

The Generations and Gender Survey (GGS) Quick Guide

Sample and Design

Design: Cross-national and longitudinal survey on the life course and family dynamics using web and face-to-face interviews.

Target sample: Nationally representative sample of 10,000 individuals aged 18-79.

Sampling strategy: Probability sampling.

For more information see the [Technical Guidelines](#).

Getting Started with GGS

GGS-I and GGS-II data and **harmonised histories** can be accessed from the [GGP User Space](#) upon registration with an institutional email.

The **standardisation** of each country's data enables easy **cross-country comparison**.

The data is available in different formats: **Stata, SPSS, Excel**

Data Documentation

The GGS documentation is available online on the GGP Colectica portal. For each country, it contains:

- Description of the fieldwork.
- Questionnaires and codebooks.
- Country-specific deviations.

Other useful resources on the website:

- [Overview of GGS-II country questions](#)
- [Overview of GGS-II country response options](#)
- [GGP User Syntax](#)

GGS-I and GGS-II

GGS-I: First round of data collection. Took place between 2004 and 2012.

GGS-II: Second round of data collection with enhanced survey design, refined questionnaire and refreshed samples.

GGS map key

- GGS-II countries
- GGS-I countries
- GGS-I & II countries

GGS-II Country Deviations

Country codes: Three-digit country identifiers (e.g., 240).

Country-specific variables: Additional or modified questions to the baseline questionnaire are identified by a suffix of the country code plus a number (e.g., dem01_2401).

Country-specific values: Non-compliant responses to the baseline questionnaire are coded as the country code plus a number (e.g., 2401, 2402...).

See the [GGP Data Processing Manual](#) for more information.

Special values

Code	Label
.a	Don't know
.b	Refusal
.c	Not applicable
.d	Never
.e	Not at all
.f	Mainly work from home
.g	Not working or homemaker
.h	Incomplete survey

GGS-II Weights

Weights are calculated for each country to account for **sample design** and **selectivity** in responses to better replicate the population distribution.

Population data is used to make country-comparative research more reliable.

Weighted **distribution** and **regressions** should be performed to account for any bias in the data.

Visit the [GGP Website](#) for more information

Generations & Gender Programme